

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

METHODOLOGICAL SYSTEM OF IMPLEMENTATION OF SUB-STANDARDS ON THE CONTENT LINE "STATISTICS AND PROBABILITY" IN MATHEMATICS IN THE VI GRADE OF SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract

In the article, the contents of the topics considered necessary and the substandards adequate for them are presented in the content of the subject of Mathematics in the VI classes of the general education schools in the content line "Statistics and Probability". Attention is directed to the technology of turning the content elements that perform the "enabling function" into action in the students' cognition in the formation of skills on sub-standards (the corresponding part of the expected results). In the "Statistics and Probability" content line, transformable elements "Data collection", "Building a table that characterizes the change of the selected data", "Diagram", "Histogram", "Numerical mean, mode and median", "Providing forecasts", "Probability", "Unlikely and very likely events", "Number of possible cases", "The number of favorable cases in relatively complex events" it is considered appropriate to make it into a system on topics. It should be noted that the task system, which serves as a means of organizing and managing the educational process for mastering the content elements on the topics presented by the students, should contain the verbs required to be performed on the mentioned topics. Examples of tasks of that kind are included in the content of the work.

Keywords: teaching process; teaching unit; content lines; standard; system; methodological system; "system-structure" approach; paradigm; information; diagram; histogram; fashion; median; event; favorable situation.

The actuality of the subject. There are no recommendations useful to be adopted for guidance in the teacher's activity in the currently used textbook complex and various teaching literature about content lines, activity lines, teaching units, expected results, main standards, substandards, and topics determined adequate to the standards in the subject of mathematics. This is very useful in terms of teaching the process of teaching mathematics according to the curriculum model. It is not denied that the continuous improvement of the teaching process in the subject is logical, most didactic problems are eternal [4-5]. Of course, as the experience of using the curriculum is formed, the methodical system of the teaching process adequate to it should be improved. Based on this logic "Mathematics in the VI class of secondary schools" Statistics and probability" methodical system of realization of substandards according to the content line We claim the relevance of the research of the topic.

Interpretation of generalizations based on information obtained on the basis of research.

Scientific sources indicate that "training" and "educational activity" are one of the main concepts of pedagogy. Although training is an important characteristic of educational activity, it does not cover all aspects of it. By the way, let's emphasize that to get to the essence of these and many other pedagogical concepts, to give an honest scientific interpretation, based on the idea of

L. Bertalanfi, in our opinion, is a successful approach. [12; 8].

Training, in the broadest sense of the word, involves the acquisition of new knowledge, skills and habits. However, learning and learning activities are essentially different events. Appropriation is an integral part not only of the learning process, but of every field of activity [2;150].

The analysis of the materials obtained from scientific sources leads us to the conclusion that training is a way of implementing education, and the fact that spiritual learning, memorizing what has been learned, and acquiring the experience of creative activity based on it depends on the way of learning (the dialectic of the content and form of cognitive action). Forming a model of educational implementation in didactics is a perennial problem [13].

The technology of education implementation (methodology in the traditional approach) has its own system [1]. The expected result in the mentioned technological system is determined by the state of movement of the selected content. There is a technological system according to each content line, teaching unit, standard, subject. It is not accidental that they are brought to the center of attention in the design of the mentioned system [3; 282-283].

Mathematics in secondary schools "Statistics and Probability" the content line has its own place [7; 575-

588]. "Statistics and Probability" content standards in the process of teaching the topics covered in the content line -5.1.1. Formulates appropriate questions to collect the necessary statistical data; 5.1.2. Creates a table, diagram (histogram as its type) that characterizes the change of selected data according to certain characteristics; 5.1.3. Finds the mode, median and mean of the collected numerical data; 5.1.4. Makes predictions based on data analysis; 5.2.1. Determines the number of possible test results; 5.2.2. Differentiates low-probability and high-probability events; 5.2.3. Finds the number of favorable cases in relatively complex cases kept in focus by being formulated as [6; 889-899].

Mastering the materials on this content line enriches the students' active mathematical vocabulary with the concepts of probability, statistical information, change of data, mode, median, numerical mean, event, complex event, non-probable and multi-probable events, test, diagram, histogram concepts and the relationships between them. makes it possible.

As an additional resource in teaching materials on the content line "statistics and probability" it is advisable to use virtual tools (from the important links for teaching the course-<https://mathway.com/graph>; <https://go/hrw/com/math/midma/gradecontrnt/manipulatives/GrpCalc/graphCalc.html>) and various working sheets [10-11].

It follows from the research that the greatest importance of studying by students in the process of teaching the topic "data collection", which is included in the content line "Statistics and probability", lies in the fact that they are taught the ability to collect the necessary information for solving various problems. It is enough to spend 2 hours on this process.

It is known that in every life situation, the right decision is made when the necessary information is available. Before making any decision, it is necessary to collect certain information. This information can be collected in various ways.

In order to collect information, the problematic situation should be defined, the methods of information collection should be clarified, the questions that serve to collect information should be selected, it should be determined whether the collected information is true or not, etc.

The teacher says that there is a special field of activity dealing with these issues. That field is called "Statistics". The teacher provides such information to the students about the field of employment of "Statistics": Statistics deals with the collection, processing, comparison and analysis of information. Its purpose is to help people solve certain problems.

Based on what we mentioned in the process of teaching the subject, it is useful for students to be involved in the following studies.

Research 1. You want to sell newspapers in your spare time, but you can only devote a certain part of the day to this business. In order to make the right decision in each area, it is important to have certain information. What you need to determine to determine if a newspaper selling business is feasible: 1) Which newspapers sell the most? 2) What time of the day are sales more? 3) In which part of the city should you organize a sale?

4) How should the price be set? 5) Is there competition in this field? and so on.

Research 2. You want to buy a quality computer at an affordable price. You need to have some information to make the right decision. The following can be attributed to this information: 1) Where are computers sold? 2) What is their selling price? 3) Which company produced the computer? 4) How is its quality? 5) What guarantee does the company provide? 6) What is the quality of work of the guaranteeing firm? and so on.

The teacher asks the following question: To what extent does the information collected based on the questions help to make any decision? [10;159]

Students' opinions are listened to.

In the process of teaching the subject, tasks are systematized according to the research question "What is the importance of formulating relevant questions for data collection?" and are offered to students in groups or groups (on worksheets).

After the groups have presented their work, ideas about the importance of formulating relevant questions in obtaining statistical information are summarized.

Summarizing the collected materials, it is concluded that the "Statistics and Probability" content line "Building a table that characterizes the change of the selected data" is enough to devote 3 hours to the teaching of the subject, and it is appropriate to formulate the student skills intended for the teaching of this subject as follows: Constructs a table or diagram that characterizes the change of selected data according to certain characteristics.

Collecting information is not enough to make certain decisions. It is important to present the collected data in various forms for processing and analysis. This is the most commonly used form of presentation. But the schedule should be made in a convenient form.

Therefore, the teacher involves the students in the research activity related to the construction of the table in a convenient form and learns the opinions of the students about why the presented form of the table is convenient.

In the teaching of the topic, it is recommended to formulate the research question as follows: What is the importance of creating a table in presenting information?

Students can work in groups or pairs to conduct research. Here, the teacher can give students the opportunity to freely choose the area where they will collect information.

Example:

Group I. "Guys, what kind of sport would you like to play? - answer the question and make a table. In what form is it convenient to give the table? (Each student can suggest his own table form).

Group II. In order to choose the class leader, it was necessary to conduct a survey among students and draw up a table reflecting the results of the survey. In your opinion, what questions should be included in the survey for the correct selection of the leader? Make a schedule.

Group III. Systematize the answers to the question "Which art would you like to have in the future?" and make a table. Determine what percentage of the whole

class is the number of students who choose each art [10;160-161].

Discussion of group presentation. Each group makes a table by formulating relevant questions. The table form is demonstrated during the presentation and evaluated by the students. Evaluation is based on the clarity, concreteness, goal-oriented construction of the questions put to the collection of information, etc. is taken into account. The originality of the selected table form is evaluated by the same rule.

At the end of the process, the teacher summarizes the opinions expressed about the importance of tables in collecting and presenting information, and notes the importance of presenting information in the form of tables.

Summarizing the collected materials, it is concluded that the "Statistics and Probability" content line "DiagramIt is enough to devote 3 hours to the teaching of the subject, and it is appropriate to formulate the student skills intended for the teaching of this subject as follows:Constructs a table or diagram that characterizes the change of selected data according to certain characteristics.

The forms of selection of the diagram, which are considered forms of information presentation, should also be appropriate. Various diagram forms are presented to the students through the computer. Questions are asked that determine which diagram shapes students recognize. Examples of these forms are described by students on the board. The teacher summarizes the information that the students said about the types of diagrams and lists them sequentially.

Research is being conducted around the question "What is the importance of constructing a diagram in presenting information?"

In the process of teaching the subject, tasks are systematized according to the research question "What is the importance of constructing a diagram in the presentation of information?" and are offered to students in groups or groups (on worksheets).

The construction of the diagram can be given in one of the office programs on the computer. The teacher shares his ideas about the importance of the diagram in collecting and presenting information, summarizes what has been learned about the forms of the diagram and when it is appropriate to use which form.

It is recommended to conduct the assessment in the lesson according to the levels reflected below.

Level I: Has difficulty constructing a diagram that characterizes the change in data.

Level II: Constructs a diagram that characterizes the change of information with a specific instruction.

Level III: Constructs an appropriate diagram that characterizes the change in information.

Summarizing the collected materials, it is concluded that the "Statistics and Probability" content line "HistogramIt is enough to allocate 2 hours of time to the teaching of the subject, and it is appropriate to formulate the student skills envisaged in the teaching of this subject as follows:It builds a table or diagram that characterizes the change of selected data according to certain characteristics [6; 892].

As a type of chart, it is considered appropriate to talk about the histogram separately. So, this type of diagram is more convenient for characterizing the change of information between certain intervals. In class V, students learned to construct a histogram for some data. Here, it is recommended that students construct a histogram of variable data with the help of Microsoft Word office software.

In the lesson, the research question can be formulated as follows: In what cases is it convenient to build a histogram?

Students are divided into pairs for the purpose of research. On the worksheets given to them, they construct the histogram according to the task both by hand and on the computer.

At the end of the lesson, the teacher lists the cases in which the histogram is constructed. Emphasizes the role of the histogram in presenting data that varies over intervals.

Summarizing the collected materials, it is concluded that the "Statistics and Probability" content line "Mean, mode and medianIt is enough to allocate 2 hours of time for the teaching of the subject, and it is appropriate to formulate the student skills intended for the teaching of this subject as follows:Finds the mode, median, and mean of the collected numerical data.

The teacher asks the students questions in order to ask them what they know from the lower grades about finding the numerical mean, the largest difference, the mode and the median of the given numbers. Students' answers are listened to.

Students should know that finding the numerical mean, greatest difference, mode, and median (statistical mean) of a numerical series is of great importance for data analysis and drawing conclusions.

The teacher gives a detailed explanation about the numerical mean, mode and median. Here, the teacher can explain to the students that the concept of the largest difference indicates the length of the numerical sequence. It should be made clear to the students that the difference between the largest and the smallest number participating in the numerical sequence is taken as "the length of the numerical sequence". In the process of teaching the subject, students should be informed about bimodal numbers.

In teaching the subject, the research question is defined as follows: What is the role of finding the numerical mean, mode, and median in data analysis?

In the process of teaching the subject, the tasks are systematized according to the research question "What is the role of finding the numerical average, mode, and median in the analysis of data?" and are offered to students in groups or groups (on worksheets) [11].

At the end of the process, the teacher should note that finding the numerical mean, mode and median, based on the results of the research, plays a major role in solving many vital issues. It emphasizes the importance of finding these quantities in making any decision, in comparison, in examining how realistic the results are.

Located in the "Statistics and Probability" content line, "Making predictionsIt is enough to allocate 2 hours of time to the teaching of the subject, and it is

appropriate to formulate the student skills envisaged in the teaching of this subject as follows: Makes predictions based on data analysis.

The teacher addresses the class with the question "How can you tell whether any event will happen or not?". Students' opinions are listened to. Then the teacher clarifies the question: "How is it predicted that the weather will be sunny tomorrow?" Again, students' opinions are listened to. "What other events can be predicted?" - the question is voiced by the teacher. There are discussions about how to make predictions about earthquakes, hurricanes, strong winds, and the speed of sea waves (it is appropriate to prepare a presentation on a computer).

The teacher addresses the class and gives information on how to make predictions of simpler events. He says that forecasts are made based on data analysis.

The teacher reminds the students that in the previous lessons we dealt with the issues of gathering, processing and presenting information. He suggests to them to discuss about giving predictions.

Continuing with this process, the following text poses a research question: Why is forecasting necessary?

The teacher informs the students about the functions of the forecast.

Tasks in the process of teaching the subject "Why is it necessary to make a forecast?" Systematized according to the research question, it is offered to the students in groups or groups (on worksheets).

In the teaching of the subject, it is recommended to conduct the assessment on the levels reflected below.

Level I: Has difficulty making predictions by analyzing data.

Level II: Analyzes the data and makes a close prediction.

Level III: Freely predicts by analyzing data.

Located in the "Statistics and Probability" content line, "Probability" it is enough to allocate 2 hours of time for the teaching of the subject, and it is appropriate to formulate the student skills intended for the teaching of this subject as follows: Determines the number of possible outcomes of trials.

The teacher brings to the students' attention that when predicting whether any event will happen in life, we often use such expressions: "it is impossible", "most likely...", "you can be one hundred percent sure that..." . Thus, we draw certain conclusions based on the analyzed data. You know that there are three types of events: "probable event", "impossible event", "random event". An event that will definitely happen based on given conditions is called a probable event. An event that will never happen under given conditions is called an impossible event. An event that either happens or does not happen based on given conditions is called a random event [10;171-172].

The teacher interprets various events, students' opinions about the possibility or impossibility of this or that event are heard (those events can be displayed on the computer in the form of slides).

By discussing several events, the characteristics of probable, improbable and random events are con-

sciously perceived by the students. The research question in the lesson is as follows: How is the type of event determined?

In the process of teaching the subject, tasks are systematized according to the research question "How is the type of event determined?" and are offered to students in groups or groups (on worksheets).

In the teaching of the subject, it is recommended to conduct the assessment on the levels reflected below.

Level I: Makes mistakes when determining the type of event.

Level II: Identifies the type of event, but has difficulty explaining the idea.

Level III: Freely defines the type of event.

Summarizing the collected materials, it is concluded that the "Statistics and Probability" content line "Low-probability and high-probability events" it is enough to allocate 2 hours of time to the teaching of the subject, and it is appropriate to formulate the student skills envisaged in the teaching of this subject as follows: It distinguishes between low-probability and high-probability events.

The teacher gives examples of events that are more or less likely to happen:

1. A coin has two sides, and the event of any of the heads falling is equally likely, because both of these faces are equally likely to fall.

2. There are 3 pens in the box. One of these pens is red and two are blue. Shamkhal took a pencil without looking at the box. At this time: a) the sky pencil comes out; b) Is the event of the red pen coming out equally probable?

Each event is discussed.

In the teaching of the topic, the research question can be formulated as follows: When are events less likely or more likely?

The class is divided into groups for the purpose of research. In the worksheets given to each group, the teacher gives tasks in such a way that, based on that task, the students distinguish the events that are more or less likely to happen.

At the end of the process, the teacher should generalize about low-probability and high-probability, equally probable events.

In the teaching of the subject, it is recommended to conduct the assessment on the levels reflected below.

Level I: Makes mistakes when determining the probability and probability of an event.

Level II: Determines the probability and probability of an event, but has difficulty explaining its meaning.

Level III: Freely correctly determines the probability and probability of an event.

Located in the "Statistics and Probability" content line, "Number of possible cases" it is enough to allocate 2 hours of time to the teaching of the subject, and it is appropriate to formulate the student skills envisaged in the teaching of this subject as follows: Determines the number of possible outcomes of trials.

The teacher poses the following problem to the students: how many two-digit numbers can be written using each of the numbers 0, 2, and 5 once? Time is given for research. All possible cases are written on the

board: 20, 25, 50, 52. As you can see, the number of possible cases here is four.

Another task is used and the number of possible cases is determined as follows:

- Aykhan forgot the code of the entrance door, but he remembered that it consisted of four digits - "0" and "1". How many cases does he have to look at before he can open the door?

Solution: By default, the door code consists of four digits, and only the digits "0" and "1" are included in the writing. So, in writing the code, there can be three "0" and one "1", two "0" and two "1" and three "1" and one "0".

Each case is investigated:

1) Cases with three "0" and one "1": 0001; 0010; 0100; 1000 - 4 cases;

2) Cases with two "0" and two "1": 0011; 0101; 0110; 1010; 1100; 10001- 6 cases;

3) Cases with one "0" and three "1": 0111; 1011; 1101; 1110 - 4 cases.

Thus, it is determined that there are only 14 possible outcomes [10;175-177].

Points to note: Students sometimes find it difficult to understand the phrase "possible cases". For this reason, the teacher should work as much as possible so that the students understand the meaning of this expression for each observed event.

In the teaching of this topic, it is advisable to apply the following research question: How to determine the number of possible cases for an event to occur or not?

In the process of teaching the subject, the tasks "How to determine the number of possible cases for an event to occur or not?" - Systematized according to the research question, it is offered to the students in groups or groups (on worksheets).

Generalization and inference: The teacher shares his ideas about methods of determining the number of possible outcomes in various events.

It is recommended to evaluate the level of efficiency of the process on the levels reflected below.

Level I: Difficulty in determining the number of possible cases of an event occurring.

Level II: Determines the number of possible cases of occurrence of the event with the direction of the teacher.

Level III: Descriptively defines the number of possible occurrences of an event.

Located in the "Statistics and Probability" content line, "A favorable number of cases in relatively complex cases It is enough to allocate 2 hours of time to the teaching of the subject, and it is appropriate to formulate the student skills envisaged in the teaching of this subject as follows: Finds the number of favorable cases in relatively complex cases.

Before teaching this topic, the number of possible cases of occurrence of the event was investigated, students acquired sufficient knowledge and skills. During this lesson, among the possible cases, the cases that are favorable for the occurrence of the event and their number are examined.

The following event (example) is called by the teacher, and the number of possible outcomes of this event and the number of favorable cases are discussed and clarified:

Research 1. What is the number of favorable occasions when a die is rolled with a score greater than 4?

Solution: There are 6 possible cases in a single roll of the dice. Since the scores greater than 4 are 5 and 6, the number of favorable cases is 2.

Investigation 2. Two dice are rolled. Find the number of favorable cases for the event that the sum of the points falling face up is 7.

Solution: We know that there are 36 possible outcomes when two dice are tossed simultaneously. Those with a total of 7 points falling on the upper face are: (1,6); (2,5); (3,4); (4,3); (5,2); (6,1). The event that the total number of points is 7 is considered favorable and their number is 6 [6; 896].

In this lesson, it is recommended to formulate the research question as follows: How to determine the number of favorable cases in complex events?

In the process of teaching the subject, tasks are systematized according to the research question "How to determine the number of favorable cases in complex events?" and are offered to students in groups or groups (on worksheets).

Generalization and conclusion: The teacher summarizes how the number of favorable cases is determined in relatively complex cases.

It is recommended to conduct the assessment in the lesson according to the levels reflected below.

Level I: Difficulty in determining the number of favorable occasions for an event to occur.

Level II: Determines the number of favorable cases of the occurrence of the event with the direction of the teacher.

It is appropriate to benefit from the criteria and tasks presented below [11] in determining the achievements of students in the content line "Statistics and Probability" (in the small summative evaluation process).

Small summative assessment criteria

1. Apply appropriate questions to collect statistical data.

2. Creates a table that characterizes the change of information.

3. Builds a diagram that characterizes the change of information.

4. Finds the mean, mode and median.

5. Makes a forecast based on data analysis.

6. Defines the type of event.

7. Determines whether the event is unlikely or highly probable.

8. Determines the number of possible cases of occurrence of the event.

9. Determines the number of favorable cases in relatively complex events.

Small summative assessment tasks

Surname: _____ First name: _____

Number of correct answers: _____

Number of wrong answers: _____ Score: _____

1. To gather information about what your classmates will be doing during the summer holidays, formulate some relevant questions:

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____
4. _____
5. _____

2. In the cinema, 15% of the audience consisted of people aged 8-12 years, 12% 12-16 years, 25% 16-20 years, 11% 20-24 years, and the rest 24-28 years. Determine the number of people in the 24-28 age range. Build a histogram according to the data.

3. Show the data given in exercise 2 in the form of a table and a pie chart.

4. Based on the given table, it is possible to predict which athlete will win the next competition?

Athletes	Number of games won	Number of lost games	The result
I	12	12	
II	8	16	
III	11	14	
IV	15	10	

5. a number is between 1 and 8 numbers, and b number is between 12 and 15 numbers. Tell your thoughts about the occurrence of events, also waiting for the following conditions:

- a) _____ $a > b$
- b) _____ $a < b$
- c) _____ $a = b$

d) $a + b$ is an even number

d) $a + b$ sum is located between 1 and 15 numbers

6. In how many ways can the names Nail, Huseyn, Samir be arranged by changing their place? What are these cases called?

7. There are 15 white and 12 one yellow balls of the same size in the bag. Without looking, they took 1 ball from the bag. Arrange the following events in order of increasing probability of occurrence:

- a) the white ball was removed;
- b) the yellow ball was removed;
- c) the ball was removed;
- d) the apple was removed.

8. Find the number of possible and favorable cases of the event that the sum of the points that come up 5 when two dice are tossed once.

9. During the lotto game, there are stones numbered from 1 to 90 in the bag. A stone is removed without looking into the bag. What is the number of favorable cases for this stone to be an even number?

10. The numerical mean of the numbers a , b and c is 18. If so $a = 4$, find the sum of $b + c$

The result. 1) "Mathematics" in the VI grade of secondary schools "Statistics and probability" in the content line in the process of teaching the covered topics, the selection and application of task types should be focused on in order for students to become subjects of the verbs based on the expected results;

2) "Mathematics" in the VI grade of secondary schools "Statistics and probability" content line the inclusion of necessary terms in the content of the students' active mathematical vocabulary in the process of teaching materials should be considered as an important didactic requirement;

3) "Mathematics in the VI class of secondary schools "Statistics and probability" content line it is advisable to use virtual tools (important links for teaching the course) and various worksheets as an additional resource in teaching materials on;

4) "Mathematics" in the VI grade of secondary schools "Statistics and probability" content line dialectic unity ("system-structure" approach-whole-part relations) should be expected between the materials on both the whole (with the content covered by the subject of Mathematics as a whole) and between the elements of the parts (of the other four content lines) belonging to each content line;

5) Expectation of the "opportunity-movement-quality" paradigm in the selection of tasks, making them into a system, has a positive effect on the efficiency of the educational process.

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